

Mechanical properties of radar-absorbing structure with nickel-electroless-plated glass fabric

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a nickel-coated glass/epoxy radar absorbing structure(RAS) was designed and verified for its structural reliability to apply it to practical structures. The conventional radar absorbing structure was fabricated by dispersing nanoparticles such as carbon black (CB), carbon nanotube (CNT) or multi-walled nanotubes (MWNT) in a polymer matrix. However, the matrix control method increases the viscosity of the matrix, which results in difficult fabrication, deterioration of mechanical properties due to agglomeration of nanoparticles and difficulties in manufacturing a curved structure. In this study, nickel-coated glass fabric via electroless plating method was used to overcome these limitations, and a radar absorbing structure with an absorption performance of -10dB (90% absorption) in the X-band (8.2-12.4 GHz) was implemented. Mechanical properties were also obtained through tensile, compressive and shear tests. Tensile strength and modulus were similar to pristine glass/epoxy. Based on these results, structural stability and reliability of RAS with absorption performance in the X-band were confirmed.

1 Introduction

Composite materials are composed of reinforcement and matrix and are classified as a next generation materials because they offer not only superior specific strength and specific stiffness but also the multi-functionality by adding filler into the matrix system. One special example of the multi-functionality is the electromagnetic wave absorbing performance by adding electrically conductive nano-material fillers such as carbon black (CB), carbon nanotube (CNT) or multi-walled nanotubes (MWNT) into the polymer matrix. These electromagnetic absorbing composites have been applied in military field as radar absorbing structures (RAS) due to their good mechanical properties and electromagnetic absorbing performance.

In the case of conventional radar absorbing structures, a high weight percentage of nano-materials in the polymer matrix is required to satisfy the electrical requirements of the RAS. Consequently, these high weight percentages of nano-materials increase the viscosity and dispersion becomes difficult causing some disadvantages. Firstly, the mechanical properties are degraded by decreasing fibre volume fraction (v_f %) due to high viscosity [1-2]. In addition, mechanical and electromagnetic properties exhibit inhomogeneous distribution due to the uncertainty in the degree of dispersion [3]. In terms of actual applicability especially curved shapes and surfaces are hard to realize [4].

To overcome these drawbacks, a fiber coating method was introduced. By coating a ferromagnetic material such as nickel or cobalt on the glass fiber, the permittivity required for the electromagnetic wave absorber can be obtained [5-6].

However, studies on the mechanical properties of nickel-coated glass fiber have mainly focused on electrical properties so far. Therefore, in this study the mechanical properties of nickel-coated glass/epoxy were evaluated to ensure reliability and stability for practical applications.

2 Radar-absorbing structure

2.1 Electroless plating nickel coated glass/epoxy

Electroless plating nickel coated glass fabric for the radar absorbing structure was purchased from Ajin-electrons (Korea). The glass fabric was uniformly coated with a 30~40nm thickness of Nickel by an electroless coating method. EDS(Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy) analysis and SEM(Scanning electron microscope) photography were carried out to confirm a successful coating. As a result, it was validated that the nickel composition was increased to 0.69 at.% compared with the pristine glass fabric. Figure 1 shows the SEM image of Ni-coated glass fabric and its EDS results.

Figure 1. The scanning electron microscope(SEM) image of Ni coated glass fabric and Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy(EDS) results of Ni coated glass fabric

To obtain the electromagnetic properties of the nickel-coated fabric, the complex permittivity was measured in the X-band (8.2-12.4 GHz) using free space equipment. The measurement results are presented in Figure 2. As shown in Figure 2 (a), the pristine glass fabric's permittivity is $4.62-j0.06$ @ 10 GHz, and the nickel-coated glass fabric's permittivity is $8.74-j10.39$ @ 10 GHz.

Figure 2. Complex permittivity of Ni-coated glass fabric and pristine glass fabric; (a) Real permittivity; (b) Imaginary permittivity

2.2 Principle of radar-absorbing structure

In this study, the Dallenbach type electromagnetic wave absorber was implemented. The principle of the Dallenbach absorber is to match input impedance values by adjusting the permittivity of materials and the thickness of each layer. Impedance values can be expressed as equivalent circuits by applying the transmission line theory as shown in the following equation [7].

$$Z_i = Z_c \frac{Z_L + Z_c \tanh \gamma_c d_i}{Z_c + Z_L \tanh \gamma_c d_i} \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), Z_i represents the input impedance of the i -th layer, Z_{L_i} is the load impedance of the i -th layer, Z_{c_i} is the characteristic impedance of the i -th layer, γ_{c_i} is the propagation constant of the i -th layer, and d_i is the thickness of the i -th layer.

The reflection loss of the absorber is given by the following equation.

$$\text{return loss}[dB] = 20 \log \left| \frac{Z_i - Z_0}{Z_i + Z_0} \right| \quad (2)$$

In equation (2), Z_0 represents the intrinsic impedance value of free space. From the above equation (2), the return loss is larger as the input impedance Z_i is closer to Z_0 . Therefore, the permittivity and thickness of the material should be adjusted to match the input impedance value with the intrinsic impedance value of the free space to have the largest return loss. The input impedance value can be obtained by a genetic algorithm that finds the maximum peak value at 10GHz with two parameters, the permittivity and the thickness.

2.3 Fabrication and microwave absorption performance of radar-absorbing structure

As a result of the genetic algorithm using the permittivity of nickel-coated glass fabric and pristine glass fabric, the optimum radar absorbing structure consist of a double-layer structure with a total thickness of 3.12 mm. The thickness of the outer layer of nickel-coated glass fiber is 0.47 mm and the thickness of the second layer of glass fiber is 2.65 mm. When actually fabricated, a 3.2 mm electromagnetic wave absorber was fabricated. Figure 3 shows the fabrication process of the proposed RAS.

Figure 3. Fabrication process flow of Ni coated glass/epoxy composite

The results of the electromagnetic simulation program CST (computer simulation technology) analysis and the measurement of the fabricated RAS using the Free space equipment are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Experimental and simulated microwave absorption performance

The proposed radar absorbing structure has an absorption performance of over -10 dB at X-band (8.2 to 12.4 GHz). CST analysis yields a maximum performance of -48.77 dB at a center frequency of 10.1 GHz. The experimentally obtained maximum absorption performance, measured by Free space equipment is located at 10.3 GHz and has an altitude of -35dB.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Mechanical test

The specimens for the mechanical tests were fabricated with plain-type glass fabric coated with nickel. As matrix YD-128 epoxy and TH-431 hardener supplied by Kukdo Chemical (Korea) were mixed at a ratio of 100: 60.

Tensile, compressive and V-notch shear tests were carried out to identify the mechanical properties. Specimens dimension and test conditions were according to ASTM D3039/D3039M[8] for tensile tests and ASTM D3410/D3410M[9] for compressive tests. Finally, the shear tests followed the requirements of ASTM D5379/D5379M[10]. The strength and elastic modulus values of each experiment are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. The mechanical properties of the Ni-glass/epoxy composites; (a) tensile, compressive and shear strength; (b) tensile, compressive and shear modulus

The tensile, compressive and shear strengths in the warp direction are 238.59 MPa, 134.19 MPa, and 30.20 MPa, respectively. In the warp direction a tensile strength of 221.96 MPa could be measured. Moreover, compressive and shear strength in warp direction turned out as 124.62 MPa and 29.93 MPa respectively, as shown in Figure 6 (a). Tensile, compressive, and shear tensile moduli are 31.83 GPa, 22.36 GPa and 1.44 GPa, respectively, in the warp direction and 25.51 GPa, 20.11 GPa and 1.83 GPa, in the fill direction as shown in Figure 6 (b). When the tensile strength and modulus values of pristine glass/epoxy and Ni-glass/epoxy were compared, the difference was within the error range. Therefore, even when Ni is coated on a glass fabric, the tensile properties are hardly degraded. This is caused by the dominant tensile properties of the fibers within the composite. According to the rule of mixture, when the bonding between the fiber and the polymer epoxy is perfect, the mechanical properties in the longitudinal direction of the composite are dominated by the fiber [11]. In fact, it is considered that assumption of perfect bonding is supported by the fact that the nickel-electroless-plated fibers have increased interfacial strength [12]. The mechanical properties in warp and fill direction are different because the number of fibers included in the yarn is varies.

Figure 6. Failure mode of Ni-glass/epoxy composite; (a) tensile, (b) compressive and (c) shear test respectively

In case of failure, the tensile test shows that it occurs in the grip and gage part such as LAT(Lateral At grip/tab Top), and AGM(Angled Gage Middle) as shown in Figure 7 (a). Compressive test results showed that the failure modes of HAT(Through-thickness at grip top) were the most common. The V-notch test results showed that the crack tip is located at the top and bottom of the V-shaped part when measuring G12, the shear modulus of fill direction from warp direction, corresponding to the MGN(horizontal and vertical cracking at gage section between notch) failure mode. The failure modes that the specimen exhibited proved that it is acceptable to measure the mechanical properties of the nickel-coated composite according to the ASTM standard for composite.

4 Conclusion

By now, conventional radar absorbing structure is fabricated by dispersing nanoparticles with a high weight fraction in a polymer matrix. This method has severe limitations including manufacturing problems due to increasing viscosity of the polymer matrix, mechanical properties deterioration due to decreasing fiber volume fraction, and uncertainties of mechanical properties like the stress concentration phenomenon.

In this study a radar absorbing structure with nickel - coated glass fabric was fabricated to overcome these limitations and its electrical and mechanical properties were measured.

As a result, in terms of electromagnetic properties, it had an absorption performance of 10dB(90% absorption) in the X-band(8.2-12.4GHz) with 3.2mm thickness. From a mechanical point of view, tensile, compressive and shear tests were carried out to confirm the mechanical properties of the composite. The failure modes of the new RAS composite coincide with conventional composite materials. Also, tensile strength and modulus values of the Nickel coated composite were compared with a pristine glass/epoxy yielding only differences within the error range. These results show that there is no significant difference in the fiber dominant properties such as tensile and compressive, even when Ni is coated. Similar behavior for compressive properties is to be subsequently validated. Therefore, this study shows the possibility of manufacturing radar absorbing structures without mechanical properties degradation and uncertainty, and the structural stability and reliability will be ensured through the verification process in the future.

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